

PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATION OF METONYMIES IN THE WORK “A FAREWELL TO ARMS” BY ERNEST HEMINGWEY

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Annotation: This article is about the use of metonymies in the Ernest Hemingway's work “A Farewell to Arms”, translated into Uzbek by Ibrahim Gafurov as “Alvido qurol”, the preservation of form and content in translation, and some shortcomings in translation.

Keywords: Metonymies, scientific, translation, translators, World Literature, great idea, construction, a century of scientific, phenomenon.

At the end of the XIX century and in the XX century, empires spread around the world, many peoples living in colonial oppression came to freedom, achieved the creation, restoration and construction of an independent national state. The Idea of democracy, freedom, equality, brotherhood spread widely throughout the Earth. Translation has played important role to the rapid spread of such great idea.

XX century was a century of scientific and technical development in history, including a century when translation was widely developed, writing wings.

Since the last quarter of the 20th century, translation in our homeland has entered in new way. The expansion of the press, the unparalleled expansion of the educational institutions, the increase in the level of literacy increased every year and every day of translation.

In the middle of the twentieth century, especially by the Sixties, the world literature of Uzbekistan became one of the most widely translated lands. Many talented translators have grown up in the country. Russian classical and modern literature blood-related countries, samples of literature of far away and near countries are the most valuable cultural indicator, were skillfully translated into Uzbek. The translations allowed to publish the hang of the national language, the expansion of the wealth of lugat, the use, regulation of the terms of different spheres, coordination with the norms of the language, the preparation of dictionaries in different directions.

Since the beginning of the 20th century, many translations of works created in west European languages in various fields have begun in Uzbek and this process has become more intensive over the next half century, our country plays an important

role in the development of scientific and technical potential and the expansion of eternal cultural ties with other peoples. Writers of countries, who draw our attention to themselves, in particular, It should be noted that such translation works attracted the attention of Uzbek readers, and soon many of them took place on bookshelves, becoming the favorite works of our people. In the 40 th years, Uzbek readers began to read the works of famous writers of World Literature in their native language. Abdulla Aripov translated “Faust” of Goethe, Kadir Mirmuhamedov “Odessia”, Mirtemir “Manas” Epas of Kirghiz, Muhammad Ali “ Ramayana” Epas of Indian nation, Ibrahim Gafurov “A Farewell to Arms” by Ernest Hemingway and other works were translated into Uzbek.

Ernest Hemingway's “farewell weapon” has become a favorite work of Uzbek readers within the translated works. The work is taken from the life of the writer, in which the events of the war are described. The work was translated into Uzbek by Ibrahim Gafurov and skillfully used artistic means in the work from metonymy, metaphors, synecdoche, epithets, periphrases.

Let's look at the application of metonymies in the work, the preservation of form and content in translation and some shortcomings in translation. In the first page of the book, The work was given such a description that Ernest Hemingway's “farewell weapon” novel is a fiery work written against a cruel and illogical war. The main character of the novel, Lieutenant Henry pure, in a bright Love Path, leaved the meaningless war. It is said that this novel is one of the most passionate works of the great writer.

E. Hemingway's work “Farewell to Arms” was translated into Uzbek by Ibrahim Gafurov with “A farewell weapon”. The work is very interesting, the language is also fluent, a work rich in stylistic skills, in which one can first see the expression of the power of the original Uzbek languages, as well as feel the writer's personal attitude to the language and his achievements in increasing his power. From this we tried to stylistically analyze this work. In this article, my task is to find the metonymy used in the work, analyze them and tell how it is applied to the Uzbek language, in the process of translating a work of art, metonymy is one of our main tasks, we can consider the structure and meaning of work in the Uzbek language and explain to readers the problems encountered in Based on the individual style of the writer, it is to learn whether the metonymy used in the work has new sides in terms of number and quality.

Having flowed the work, I found the metonymy in it and divided them into 5 groups according to the rule, which are as follows:

1. Metonymy can be formed on the basis of both abstract and concrete concepts of words.

2. The characteristics of a thing, phenomenon or people are transferred to the name of that thing or people.

3. The attitude of the piece to the whole or the whole to the piece (Synecdoche)

4. On the basis of the relationship between what is known and its name, another type of metonymy arises.

5. And sometimes the author's name is used instead of his work. 1. The river ran behind us and the town had been captured very handsomely but the mountains beyond it could not be taken and I was very glad the Austrians sought to want to come to the town requirements, if the war should and because they did not bombard it to destroy it but only a little in a military war³⁶.

Daryo bizning ortimizda oqardi, shaharni ham osongina qo'lga kiritdik, lekin nariroqdagi tog'larni ishg'ol qila olmadik; men shunisiga xursand edimki, avstraliyaliklar qachonlardir urush tugasa, qaytib boramiz-ku, degan o'y bo'lsa kerak, shaharni aytarli bombardimon qilishmas yo'liga po'pisa qilib qo'yardilar xolos.

Here is metonymy Us, which translates into Uzbek "bizni". Because the river does not flow behind us. The place where we live through is implied. This statement is of the tortist type of metonymy, that is, we can see the relationship between what is known and what is between it.

2. The battery in the next garden wake me in the morning³⁷.

Ertalab meni qo'shni bog'dagi batareya uyg'otib yubordi. The word "battery" refers to the hard sound emanating from the battery guns. It was not the battery that woke him up, but the hard sound emanating from the battery. In this sentence, the relationship between the thing and it is indicated. This statement belongs to the fourth type of metonymy.

3. The battery fired twice. Batareya ikki marta o'q uzdi. In this sentence, the battery indicates the meaning of the weapon, and the fourth type of metonymy shows the relationship between something and its name

4. Dont write anything that will both the censor. Senzorga ozor beradigan gaplarni yozib o'tirmang yana. Censor is metonymy in this place. The writer refers to society as a censor. An example of the fourth type of metonymy this sentence takes a child. "A regiment by in the road and I watched them pass". Yonimdagi yo'ldan polk o'tib borardi,men saflar qanday qadam tashlayotganiga qarab turar edim.

³⁶ E. Hemingway "Farewell to Arms",p 5 Charles Scribner's sons 1971

³⁷ E. Hemingway "Farewell to Arms",p 5 Charles Scribner's sons 1971

The word “Regiment” is translated into Uzbek as “polk”. The meaning of the regimental word refers to a group of soldiers made up of a many. There is no Regiment's foot he cannot walk, people are meant through the regiment. In this sentence, the fourth type of metonymy is used.

There were stragglers going by long after the regiment had passed I who could not keep up with their platoons. In the fall when the rains come the leaves all fell from the chestnut trees and branches were bare and the trunks black with rain.

Kuz kirib, yomg'ir ketidan yomg'ir quyib bergach, kashtanlarning yaproqlari duv to'kilardida, shoxlari qip-yalang'och bo'lib qoldida, daraxtlarning tepalari yomg'irdan qorayib ketti.

Today we can see in English the word “fall” instead of the word “autumn” is used. This translates as falling according to the origin of the word. In autumn, the foliage of the trees falls off. In this, the whole part is expressed. This statement refers to the third type of metonymy.

When you come back bring a phonograph “Bring good opera discs”. “Bring Caruso”. ” Dont bring Caruso. He bellows”. - Qaytib kelayotganizda grammafona obkeling. -Karuzoni opkeling. -Karuzo kerak emas uvillaydi.³⁸

In the work , Henry's friend asks him to bring a plate. In doing so, he sucks a plate of Karuzo, not his own Karuzo. That is the plate is named after the person who wrote it. In this sentence, the author's name is used instead of his work. This example belongs to the fourth type of metonymy.

Rinaldi was sitting on the bed with the copy of Hugos English grammar.

Rinaldi Hyugoning ingliz tili grammatikasini qo'lda tutib, kravatda o'tirgan ekan. In this example, the work is used under the name of the writer. Hyugo is the author who wrote the book, and the book is named after him. This statement belongs to the fifth type of metonymy.

We were in the foot-hills on the near side of the river and as a road mounted there were the high mountains off to the north with snow still on the tops.

Biz daryo tomondan tog' etagi bilan ketmoqda edik, yo'l yuqorilagach, shimol tomonda baland qorli cho'qqilar ko'rindi.

It is here that the path to the mountain is metonymy. The relationship between the thing and it is shown. In this sentence, the third form of metonymy is used.

Each work of art forms a dialectical unity of form and content. The translator, who translated Hemingway's “A Farewell to Arms” from English into Uzbek, paid

³⁸ Ibrohim G'ofurov “Alvido qurol” 96 bet. Toshkent, Yosh gvardiya 1986 y

great attention to the preservation of the original in translation of metonymy, which is one of the most complex types of migration. It is observed that the original on the basis can find an alternative option, give it its meaning and content characteristics or form stored or modified, using more scientific translation methods than transliteration, annotation and artistic translation.

This is creates new translation methods. In the process of translation, attempts to preserve the content of the text, artistic originality and artistic coloritis of the work, and while creative approaches in this regard were observed, the translator made minor flaws, in most cases, could not preserve some artistic image tools, lexical and contextual meanings of national words and phrases, as well as pictorial compactness, musical melodiousness.

And the reason for this is the fact that he adheres to the principle of more scientific and free translation.

A translator translating from an other language, ignoring every small detail, commonality and originality, may undermine the nationality of the work, and the work of art may not correctly convey the individual style and spirit of the author to the reader.

A translator who studied well the traditions, lifestyle, spirit, culture, mentality and language of the English people was able to fully give the content of the original in translation through metonymy.

The translation of Hemingway's "A Farewell to Arms" from English into Uzbek serves as an auxiliary resource for the Uzbek reader to create an idea of the English people's about a certain period (wartime) habit, way of life, spirit, culture, mentality, national character. National realities have been turned by transliteration or equivalent application, which is defined by the fact that the translation language cannot absorb the quality, causing misunderstandings for the reader. This method, which the translator used, is the most correct, which in front of the Uzbek reader views where the event took place, with of which nation, through the translation of Realis and ensures easy the implementation. In it place, the translation laid the groundwork for realies to have a place in their vocabulary by switching to the Uzbek language.

Some metonymic retreats be translation of Hemingway's "A Farewell to Arms" into Uzbek made it possible to preserve not only the meaning and content of the original on the basis of the laws of the English language, but also its artistic style, a set of symbols and an impressive spirit. In addition, this work was presented to Uzbek readers as a kind of artistic and scientific work.

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